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RECENT ADVANCES IN LIPOSOMAL DRUG DELIVERY: FROM FORMULATION TO THERAPEUTIC APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

In this review article, we learned about liposomes, which are one type of drug delivery system that can be used to target a specific tissue. The structure if a lipid bilayer and the cell membrane are similar, which allows liposomes to deliver drugs to the places where free drugs would not be able to enter, The other drug delivery methods include pharmacosomes, micro particles, released erythrocytes and noisome. In the middle of the 1960s, liposomes are sphere shaped vesicles made of one or more phospholipid bilayers-were first reported. They are now a highly helpful tool vesicles in reagent and reproduction in many scientific fields, such as biology, biophysics, chemistry, colloid science biochemistry and mathematics and theoretical physics ever since, liposomes are now available for purchase. Among many innovative drug delivery methods. Liposomes stand out for their sophisticated technology in delivering active molecules to the site of action. Currently multiple formulations of liposomes are being used in clinical settings .From conventional vesicles to liposomes technology research has advanced to second generation liposomes ,in which lipid modifications are used to create long circulating liposomes composition vesicle size and charge .Additionally liposomes with altered surfaces have been utilizing multiple molecules including acid and glycolipids. This paper provides an overview of scalable methods and emphasizes the advantages and disadvantages with regard to industrial application and evaluation.

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INTRODUCTION

The term liposome was first introduced by Paul erlich in 19th century. These carrier system target drug directly to target organ such cancer he termed there vesicles as “magic bullets”[1].

Figure no: 1 Structure of liposomes.

Ref :A.Divya Novel technologies of transdermal drug delivery systems journal of pharmaceutics andnanotechnology 2015.

The liposome term was initiated from two word “lipo” which define fatty and “some” defined as Body “.A.D Bangham made the initial discovery of them in 1965[2]They discovered spontaneous self assembled closed vesicles with hydrophilic cores and concentric lipid bilayers when phospholipids were disseminated in an aqueous media[3].we offer liposomal technology for all our clinical study, supply, commercial contract , manufacturing and pre-clinical development services .The scientist had noticed that egg lecthin smears reacted with water to generate incredibly complex structures .After analysis using electron microscopy ,it was discovered that many vesicles[4].

Liposomes are self assembling, closed, spherical entities made of cholesterol and one or more lipid bilayers that are curled in a concentric manner [5]. Their size vary from 20nm to several micron. Early in the 1990s, the cytotoxic anti-cancer medication doxorubicin was introduced in its first liposomal formulation liposomes are currently employed successfully in every conceivable drug delivery method and their uses in resolving a wide range of biological issues are also growing structure of liposome [6].

Liposomes hold immense promise as a drug delivery system and continue to be the focus of extensive research and development efforts. With further advancements in formulation techniques and evaluation methodologies, liposomes are expected to play a crucial role in improving drug delivery efficiency and enhancing therapeutic outcomes in the future.

ADVANTAGES: [7]

1. Liposomes improved the drug’s therapeutic index and efficacy.
2. For systemic and non systemic administration, liposomes are non-toxic, flexible, biocompatible, fully biodegradable and non immunogenic.
3. Liposomes lessen the encapsulated agent’s toxicity.
4. Ideal for administering medications that are hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs.
5. Minimize the amount of toxic drug exposure to delicate tissues.
6. Utilized as vehicles for long- term, restricted drug .

DISADVANTAGES [8]

1. Low solubility
2. Production cost is high
3. Less shelf life.
4. Leakage and fusion of encapsulated drug.

TYPES OF LIPOSOMES [9]

Liposomes are divided into various groups:

1. Based on size of vesicle
- A. Unilamellar vesicles

TYPE OF VESICLE	SIZE
Small unilamellar vesicle [SUV]	40-80nm
Medium unilamellar vesicle [MUV]	40-100nm
Large unilamellar vesicle [LUV]	100-1000nm

B. Oligolamellar vesicle

The internal volume of oligolamellar vesicles encloses 19-30 lipid bilayers.

C. Multilamellar vesicles

They include several bilayers. The aqueous volume can be divided into multiple compartments. They vary in the manner in which they are made the setups can resemble an union a number of SUVs surrounded by concentric spherical bilayers of LUV/MLV.

2) Based on particles for preparing liposomes

- i. REV: phase evaporation process in reverse vesicles that are single, oligolamellar, or multilamellar are made using this technique.
- ii. SPLV; lurilamellar vesicles that are stable.
- iii. FATMLV: Method of freezing and throwing utilized to prepare MLV.
- iv. VET: Multiple vesicles are prepared using the extrusion method
- v. DRV: A method called dehydration – rehydration is used to prepare various kinds of vesicles.

3) Depending on the application and composition

- i. Conventional liposomes: composed of phospholipids and cholesterol, which are negatively and neutrally charged.
- ii. Fusogenic liposomes
- iii. PH sensitive liposomes: phospholipids like DOPE that have either
- iv. Long circulatory liposomes: It contains polyethylene glycol and it is termed as regulation. Regulation enhances circulation of liposomes in the body by decreasing its body clearance.

METHODS OF PREPARATION

Liposomes can be prepared using different techniques. The final liposome characteristics are significantly influenced by the phospholipids type and liposome manufacturing process. The processes used to make liposomes can be classified into following.

1. THIN FILM HYDRATION METHOD

Using a round bottom flask, all lipids and the hydrophobic medication are dissolved in an appropriate organic solvent in this method, after that, the organic solvent gradually evaporated at lower pressure to produce a thin layer of film, then the lipid's transition temperature in an aqueous buffer solution. A hydrophilic medication present in hydration solution. The rate at which you hydrate dictates the effectiveness of medication encapsulation. The slower the rate of hydration, greater the encapsulation efficiency. It is possible to control particles distribution, lamellarity types and resizing. Compared to sonication the extrusion method provides more stable liposomes with higher encapsulation efficiency. SUVs liposomes are typically produced by sonication, which can also break down sonication of probes may subject, liposomes suspension should be inspected for possible metal contamination.

Figure no: 2 thin film hydration method.

Ref: Hamdi Nsairat, Dima Khater, Liposomes: structure, composition, types, and clinical applications, heliyon, 2022, 8.

2. REVERSE PHASE EVAPORATION METHOD

These methods are generally used as an alternative to thin film hydration by the formation of water-in-oil emulsion, initially the lipids are dissolved in an organic solvent which is subsequently combined with an hydrophilic drug containing aqueous buffer. Under reduced pressure the organic solvent evaporated and results to form lipid vesicles suspended in aqueous solution. By the extrusion method average size and poly disparity of the preformed vesicles can be decreased. This method is suitable for high molecules, but however, sonication conditions and organic solvents may denature therapeutic peptides.

3. PH LEAPING METHOD

This method is another solvent free way to prepare liposomes. The phosphatides acid and phosphatides choline aqueous solution is subjected to an almost four – fold increase in pH over a brief period of time to convert MLVs into SUVs. The portion of phosphatides acid: The ratio of UVs to LUVs generate by is determined by phosphatides choline [10]

PH LEAPING METHOD:-

Figure no:3 PH Leaping method

Ref:Abeer Al Bawab , Walhan Alshaer , Liposomes: structure, composition, types, and clinical applications ,2002,VOL:8, ISS :5.

4. DETERGENT REMOVAL METHOD

In this method, around bottom flask is filled with lipids and high critical Michelle concentration (CMC) surfactant in a suitable organic solvent. After evaporation a thin film was obtained at the bottom flask. After that, by hydration of lipid film in an aqueous solution containing drug molecules a mixed micelles solution was obtained. Surfactant is then removed by dialysis .finally, a LUVs liposomes were prepared after solution concentration. During the detergent evaluation step the most of the hydrophilic drugs are separated and these are the main limitation of this method.

SOLVENT DISPERSION

Ethanol injection -When a lipid solution of ethanol is combined with an aqueous buffer ,MLVs are formed.

Ether infusion-To a solution of drug compound to be encapsulated a lipid solution is added and injected gradually using diethyl ether.

a. SONICATION

Sound waves are employed in the process of “sonication” to stir up particles in solution. This type of disruption can be used to combined solutions, dissolve solids more quickly and extract dissolved gas from liquids.

The process of converting MLVs into small unit lamellar vesicles is called sonication. The ultrasonic irradiation helps to convert MLVs to SUVs.

Figure No: 4 Bath Sonication and Probe Sonication.

Ref: Puja saha, subashish saha, liposomes, indain research journal of pharmacy, vol:10, Iss :1.

b. PROBE SONICATION METHOD

An ice bath titanium will slough off and this method is used for high energy of lipid. The tip of sonication immersed into liposome dispersion. On overheating the tip, then vesicle immersed into transishing the solution

c. BATH SONICATION METHOD –

This method is used for dilute lipids of large volume. The liposome was placed into the bath sonication by controlling the temperature of lipid. The liposomes lipid bilayer can then combined with other bilayers to release the contents of liposomes. To create liposomes, a drug or DNA solution, they can transport a lipid bilayer [11].

EVALUATION OF LIPOSOMES

The characteristics of liposomal processing and formulation for specific purpose are established to guarantee their consistency in performance in-vitro and in-vivo. The defining characteristics for the aim of evaluation.

A. VESICLE SHAPE AND LAMELLARITY:-

The electron microscope technique can be used to determine the vesicle shape. Vesicles lamellarity is determined by using an freeze-fracture imaging and P31 nuclear magnetic resonance of analysis.

B. VESICLE SIZE AND DISTRIBUTION

Different techniques are available for determining the size and distribution of vesicles. For example, fluorescent microscopy, particularly electron microscopy. Field electron microscopy transmission larger, gel formation and flow fraction. With these electron microscopy and microscopy are primarily used to establish the size range of liposomes.

C. ZETA-POTENTIAL DETERMINATION

The electron mobility of a 90° angle and was inspected by Zeta potential. By using 3000HS Zeta-seizer equipment in triplicate the measurement will be done. For the potential determination the sample is diluted with suitable solvents [12].

D. HYDRODYNAMIC METHODOLOGY

This method uses an ultra-centrifuge and gel permeation. Using big gels for chromatography was presented from MLVs to SUVs. Due to the heavy size of diameter of 1-3 the gel not entered and is retained on top of column. For the size distribution of liposomes employed a thin layer chromatography system. However, it was not indicated whether this process was susceptible to a physical obstruction of the agar gel pores similar to the more traditional column chromatography.

E. THE EFFICIENCY OF ENCAPSULATION (EE)

The amount of medication contained in the liposomes aids in estimating how the medication will behave in a biological system.

To determine the percentage of drug encapsulation, the free drug fraction and encapsulated drug fraction must first be separated. Then next, using the appropriate detergents, the encapsulated fraction is allowed to leak off the liposomes into an aqueous solution.

F. STUDY OF DRUG RELEASE

The release medium was 500ml of 20% ethanol; 10ml of the release medium was drawn and put into a dialysis bag. After that, the dialysis bag was clamped and fastened to the paddle of a device for dissolving medication, 5ml ethanol drug solution containing the same amount of drug where dissolved in turn. In the dialysis vesicle at 300×g and 37°C while stirring [13].

G. MICROSCOPIC TECHNIQUES

Optical microscopy
This microscopic technique, which is helpful in assessing vesicle quality, uses a phase contrast, fluorescent and bright field microscope. The size of the big vesicle.

Negative stain

TEM Scanning electron microscopy of negative stain TEM are the two main electron microscopy techniques used to evaluate the size and shape of liposomes. The later technique is not as favored. Electron stain negative bright are vesicle against a dark background through Microscopy. Ammonium is one of the negative stain used in TEM analysis. Ammonium molybdate and PTA are both anionic substances whereas the nature acetate is cationic.

Techniques of cryo-transmission electron microscopy

This method has been applied to clarify the size and surface of vesicles [14].

H. LASER LIGHT TECHNIQUE

Photon correlation spectroscopy examines how the Brownian motion of particles is scattered laser light causes intensity fluctuations in time of suspension or solution. Thus, the tiny particles spread more quickly than big particles, the rate of variation of dispersed. As a result, light intensity varies.

As a result of this the translating it is possible to measure the diffusion coefficient which in turn can help calculate the average hydrodynamic radius of particles by means of the Stoke-Einstein formula. By using this method particles in the 3nm range can be measured [15,16].

I. SURFACE CHARGES

Based on the free flow electrophoresis of multi-layer vesicles measurement of surface charge can be done. It makes use of a cellulose acetate plate that has been dipped in pH 8.8 sodium borate buffers.

After applying roughly 5n moles of lipid samples to the plate undergoes a 30-minute electrophoresis.

The liposomal gel undergoes bifurcation based on the changes on their surface.

This method can be applied to ascertain the degree of change heterogeneity in the liposome suspension and to find any contaminations like fatty acids [17].

APPLICATIONS OF LIPOSOMES

a. Liposomes for ophthalmic

Liposomes have demonstrated efficacy against a variety of ocular condition such as corneal transplant rejection and dry eyes .For eye condition the liposomal formulation of the medication verteporfin has been approved.

b. Liposomes in cosmetics

Because of their release pattern and resemblance to the cell membrane, liposomes are also utilized in the cosmetic industry.

c. Liposomes in Gene therapy

Liposomes are frequently used in gene therapy applications to treat illness.

d. Liposomes in Cancer treatment

Carrier liposomes have already been proven to be effective as Nano carriers the treatment of chemotherapy .For chemotherapy numerous medication formulations have already received approval [18].

e. Liposomes as carriers in oral therapy

f. Liposomes for topical use .liposomes for delivery to the lungs .

g. Liposomes in Opposing leishmaniasis

h. Liposomes in lysosomal storage

i. Application of cell biology [19,20].

CONCLUSION

This review provides an in-depth understanding of liposomes, including their structure, types, methods of preparation, evaluation techniques, advantages, and disadvantages. Liposomes offer several advantages such as improved therapeutic index, biocompatibility, biodegradability, and the ability to encapsulate both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs. They can target specific tissues and minimize drug toxicity, making them suitable for systemic and non-systemic administration. Additionally, liposomes can be tailored to meet specific requirements through modifications in composition, size, and surface properties. Despite their numerous advantages, liposomes also pose challenges such as low solubility, high production costs, and limited shelf life. Encapsulation efficiency and drug leakage are also concerns that need to be addressed during formulation.

The applications of liposomes span across various fields including oncology, ophthalmology, cosmetics, gene therapy, and oral drug delivery, among others. Marketed formulations of liposomes have already been approved for the treatment of fungal infections, cancer, ocular diseases, and other medical conditions.

MARKETED FORMULATIONS OF LIPOSOMES

Table No 1 Marketed Formulation of Liposomes [21]

BRAND NAME	GENERICNAME	INDICATION	TYPE OF FORMULATION
Ambisome®	Amphotericin B	fungal infection	Parenteral
Daunxome®	Daunorubicin	Kaposi's sarcoma	Parenteral
Doxil®	Doxorubicin	Refractory kaposi's sarcoma	Parenteral
Visudyne®	Vertiporfin	Ocular histoplasmosis	Parenteral
Depocyl®	Cytarabine	Lymphomatous meningitis	Parenteral
Lipoplatin®	Cisplatin	Epithelial malignancies	Parenteral
Depodur®	Morphine sulphate	Postoperative pain following majorsurgeries	Parenteral

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REFERENCES

1. R divya sree, k. Divya, s Arthi, k. Bhavani, M. Vamshidar, A comprehensive review on liposomes:A novel drug delivery system, International journal of pharmaceutical sciences and research 2022, vol:13, Issue2,628-644.
2. Peng liu, Guiliang chen, Jingchen zhang, A review of liposomes as a drug delivery system: current status of approved products, regulatory environments, and future perspectives, molecules, 2022vol:27, Issue:4.
3. Hamdi Nsairat, Dima khater, Usama sayed, Fadwa odeh, Abeer Al Bawab, and Walhan Alshaer, Liposomes:Structure, composition, types, and clinical applications, National library of medicine,2022, vol:8, Issue:5.
4. Kant shashi, Kumar satindher, Prashar Bharat, A complete review on liposomes, Department of pharmaceutical sciences,2012,vol:3, Issue:7.

5. M .Ramyateja, M. Nawaneesh, M. Siddu, P. Manikanya, Dr. J. N. Suresh kumar, A review on liposomes, international journal of creative research thoughts,2022, vol:10, Issue:4, 2320-2882.
6. A.Maheshwaran , P. Brindha, AR. Mulaicharam, K. Masilamani, Liposomal drug delivery system-A review, international journal of pharmaceutical sciences,2013, vol:23, Issue:1,,295-301.
7. Devendar sharma, Aashiya Aara E. Ali, Leena, R. Trivedi, An updated review on liposomes as drug delivery system, Pharma Tutor,2018, vol:6, Issue:2,8,50.
8. R.R Thenge, M. P Chandak, V. S Adhao, Liposomes: A novel drug delivery system, International journal of pharmacy, human journals,2020, vol:18, Issue:2,705-715.
9. Abolfazl Akbar aadesh, Rogaie Rezaei sadabady, soodabeh davaran, sang woo Joo, nosratollah zarghami, Liposome:classification, preparation and applications, nanoscale research letters, 2013,vol:8, Issue:102,1- 9.
10. Sriram vemuri, C, T rhodes, Preparation and characterization of liposomes as therapeutic delivery systems:A review, Pharmaceutica Acta helvetiae,1995, vol:70, Issue:2,95-111.
11. Manish kumar , Arpita singh, swarnyma pande, mohd. Aqil siddiquil, Nitish kumar, Liposomes:types , preparation, and evaluation, International journal of indigenous and herbs,1999, vol:6, Issue:1,17-21.
12. 12.J.S dua, Prof A. R rana, Dr. A. K bhandari, Liposomes: methods of preparation and applications, International journal of pharmaceutical sciences and research, 2229-4619.
13. Ganesh shankar sawant, kiran vikas sutar, Akhil s kanekhar, Liposomes: A novel drug delivery system, International journal of research and review,2021, vol:8, Issue:4.
14. Sunitha reddy M, Amulya etikala, liposomes: A novel drug delivery system: A review, Biological Sciences,2019, vol:9, Issue:4,374-382.
15. Raghavendra kumar gunda, J. N suresh kumar, Bhargavi G, Bhavani satya prasad A, sandhya B, KNVL padmaja, sriram praveen, A review on formulation and evaluation of liposomal drug, Health and medical sciences,2023., vol:4, Issue:1,31-44.
16. Meng lin, Rudong wang, Xian-rong Qui, Quality evaluation of drug loaded liposomes,2021, vol:8, Issue :1,
17. Akshay singha roy, Sudipta das, Arnab samanta, Design formulation and evaluation of liposomes containing isoniazid, Applied pharmaceutics, 2018,vol:10, Issue:2.
18. Hadis daraee, Ali etimadi, mohammad kouhi, samira alimirzalu, Applications of liposomes in medicine and drug delivery, nanomedicine and biotechnology,2016, vol:44, Issue: 1,381-391.
19. MU unhumwanga, Rs okor, current trends in the production and biomedical applications of liposomes: A review,Biomedical sciences,2005, vol: 4,Issue :1,9-21.
20. subash chandhran MP , Prasob G. R, Jagatha T, Aswathy BS, An overview on liposomal drug delivery system,pharmaceutics, 2019,vol:9, Issue:2,61-68.
21. Bandari saloni,kishnani kushbu,A concise review on liposomes drug delivery system,pharma tutor.

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